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Influence of Socioeconomic Factors on Daily Life and Quality Life of People: a case study of Biswanath town village

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Abstract

Biswanath ghat, also called popularly as 'Gupta Kashi', which is located in the middle north bank of the river Brahmaputra. Here the purpose of the study is to understand the socio-economic factors and its influence on daily life and quality life of the people living in the village. The study was based on both primary and secondary data. Structured random sampling was used to collect primary data and structured questionnaire was using for household survey. Finding of the study shows that changing occupation pattern from fishing to other activities has influence on the life of the people in the village. People of the village mainly depend on tourism activities (mainly religious tourism), weaving, fishing, petty business, ferry transportation, and service. Maps have been prepared on the basis of updated cadastral map using ArcGIS 10.3.

Keywords: 1.Socio-Economic life, 2.Fishing, 3.Changing occupation, 4.Gupta Kashi.

1. Introduction

Brahmaputra is the largest river system in north-east India. It is the seventh largest river in the world in terms of discharge (Horius, 1998; Tondon and Sinha, 2007). River channels are only part of an extensive interconnected series of biotopes and environmental gradients that, with their biotic communities, constitute fluvial systems (Ward, 1998). Assam for ages together has been a riverine civilization, society and economy (Hazarika and Bhagabati, 2020). The foundation and centre of this riverine society and economy has been and continues to be the mighty river of 'Brahmaputra'. This river has 33 tributaries which has influenced continues to influenced the social and economic life of Assam and its people (Hazarika and Bhagabati, 2020). The valley supported about 27 million people by providing land for agriculture and human habitat (Economic Survey of Assam, 2011-12). The net cultivated area of the state is 28.11 lakh hectares which is about 88 percent of the total land available for agriculture in the state (Economic Survey of Assam, 2011-12).

We recently made a detailed analysis of the socio-economic factors which influenced the people living in the Biswanath Town Village. In this paper we describe the occupational changes due to natural and anthropogenic factors and possible consequence of these changes on livelihood pattern of the people.

2. Study Area

Biswanath ghat, also called popularly as 'Gupta Kashi' located in the Biswanath district of Assam. The village is located between 26°66' N to 26°70'N latitude and from 93°17'E to 93°23'E longitude (Figure 1). Biswanath district is located in the north bank of the river Brahmaputra. Total area of the Biswanath town village is 66.29 hectare. Assam has many tourist gems. One such gem is the Biswanath ghat. Biswanath town village was the main town during the British period. Now, the town has been shifted 10 kilometers towards north, called as Biswanath Chariali town.

Biswanath ghat, though a religious place, makes for a perfect tourist destination during the winters. The water level of the Brahmaputra recedes with the coming of the winter and gives way to wish

golden riverine sand beaches for tourists to explore. The lowered water level also brings most of the rocks in the small riverine bay out from magnificent view. Biswanath town village is a cadastral village with a population of 2792 as per 2011 census. The total number of household is 577. This village is 2 kilometers away from the daily market (Na-Bazar) and 10 kilometers away from the main town.

This paper is an attempt to study the socio-economic status of the people living in the Biswanath ghat area of Biswanath town village in the bank of the river Brahmaputra.

Fig: 1 Cadastral map of Biswanath Town Village

3. Database And Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used to study the socio-economic condition of the people living in Biswanath ghat area of Biswanath town village. Secondary data have been collected from census of India 2011, Biswanath Panchayat office (01), Biswanath circle office and Assam Survey office. Primary survey also has been done through structured questionnaire administered at the household level. The study is based on intensive field work covering 577 household of the selected village was conducted with the help of Rapid Rural Appraisal (RRA) and interview with the villagers individually and in group. Besides, conversations with the village elderly were also made in order to know the socio-economic condition in depth. The survey was held on 2017 to 2019.

4. Result And Discussion

The study is based on a socio-economic study of 577 household of Biswanath town village, in Biswanath district of Assam. The location of the village is on the north bank of the river Brahmaputra. The survey gathered empirical data on demographic, education, health, employment status, poverty, caste and other indicators of social well-beings. The objective behind the survey was to use the data to find out the socio-economic status of the village people and that could address pressing local concerns and improve the living standards of the local population. The variable of caste and religion play equally important role to study the socio-economic status of the village people of Biswanath town village. In the village schedule caste (80.95%) accounted for majority among the Indigenous Assamese community. Out of the total SC population proportion of male and female population are equal. Male comprises (50.1%) and female comprises (49.9%). ST population comprises (.64%) and others (19.7%) which include both OBC and General category (2011 census). In the field survey it have found that only eleven (11) households are belongs to Brahmin family even though Biswanath

ghat has a cluster of more than 100 temples in the vicinity and it is religious place. Education status of the head is significant for analysis because education status of the head reflects in the perception of the health of the household. We observed that total literacy rate of the village is 89.29 percent which is more than the state average literacy rate. Out of which male literacy rate is 92.23 percent and female literacy rate is 80.20 percent (2011 census). It shows that literacy rate of the village is good. There are total five numbers of educational institutes in the village. Out of which two are primary schools, two are middle schools, one secondary school and eight numbers of anganwari Kendra.

The employment status is a basic indicator of economic soundness of households. Majority of people are engaged in unskilled work like fishing, cow rearing, construction work, giving temporary stalls in front of the Temple (mainly by the women and children), and daily wages activities. On the other hand major livelihood sustenance measure adopted by local people is the collection of thalway and logs of trees for self use as well as to sell in the local market as firewood. Out of the total population 857 (30.69%) are the main working population. It shows that number of unemployed person is high in females as compared to males. The domination of unskilled work among the villagers reflects uncertainty of income on their part. Out of the total working population 125 persons are engaged in government job, 178 persons are engaged in business activities, and 362 persons in other activities. Out of the total household only thirty (30) households have agricultural lands. It shows that there is a shortage of agricultural land in the village. So, agriculture based livelihood options is minimum in the village. There are some private tea gardens in the village, which occupies (27 *bigha*) of village land.

The village has experienced great changes in terms of livelihood pattern in the last fifty years. Unlike many neighboring villages that have recently started to engage in non-agricultural activities, the Biswanath town village had a considerable number of residents involved in the same. Being an ancient town, occupation like shop-keeping, boat services, fishing and various other businesses and services have always been prevalent in this area; though fishing was always the dominant form of livelihood; more than eight percent of the people being involved in fishing until the sixth addition of Kaziranga National Park (Plate 5).

The addition states that the Brahmaputra is to be considered a part of the Kaziranga National Park. This makes the river a protected territory and bans many livelihood activities of the local residents. In times prior to the sixth addition, fisherman could navigate far south in the river for bigger catches (source: field survey). People are no more allowed to do and are kept away by frequent river patrols conducted by the Department of Forest, Government of Assam.

Changes in pattern of livelihood in this village are drastic unlike the rest of the villages that have substantial amount agricultural activities as well. Only a mere twenty-seven percent of the household are still earning their livelihoods through fishing as compared to eight percent during the times of their fathers. For those who are continuing with fishing are cared to go far south for bigger catches as they face the danger of legal actions for encroaching protected areas. According to some fishermen interviewed during field surveys, fish population has dwindled greatly in the last 10 years. Rests of the fifty-three percent have resorted to other activities such as shop-keeping (nineteen percent), daily labor (eighteen percent) and services (ten percent) etc. the area has seen a dramatic increase in the number of shops in the market encompassing the Biswanath temple. However, their income is sporadic and depends highly on the festivals and picnic seasons (Table 3).

Plate:1 structure of a kutcha house

Plate 2: Collection of Logs

Plate 3: Talking with a priest

Plate 4: Shop in front of Vishwanath Temple

Plate 5: Area under sixth addition to Kaziranga National Park, which is demarcated by the north bank line of the Brahmaputra river.

Source: Field survey, 2017

4.1 Basic amenities available in the village

Living conditions of the village is mainly depending on the basic amenities available in the village. It measured through the availability of toilet, bathroom, drinking water facility, drainage, garbage disposal, electricity, cooking fuel etc. it is necessary to have a proper house. On the basis of material used in walls and roofs, we classified all houses in to three categories- pucca, semi-pucca and kutcha. A pucca house is one which is constructed with cement and concrete or tin roofing, semi pucca house is one of which either the roof or the walls but both is not made of pucca materials like burnt bricks, stone, cement, concrete or timber. A kutcha house is made up of mud with thatched and or tin sheet roofing. In the village largest numbers of houses are a semi pucca house which is comprises 55 percent of the total household. 36.7 percent are pucca house and only 8.3 percent are kutcha house. Available field data reveals that each household has a average 5 to 6 members.

Availability of the toilet is an important indicator of the sanitation. Available field data reveals that in the Biswanath town village, the entire household has their own toilet and bathroom. This village is fully electrified.

4.2 Availability of the government offices

There is one forest beat office, covering an area of (three *Bigha*) of land. One river police station and one post office are there in the village. There was a state bank of biswanath ghat branch, but now the bank is shifted from this village to six kilometers towards north to a village called Gorehagi in BG road due to the erosion of land. Now, office of the IWAI (Inland Waterways Authority of India) TERMINAL (SAGARMALA) of Biswanath ghat is set up in that area.

Table: 1
Population Data

Parameters		No. Of Population
Total Population		2792
Male		1392
Female		1400
Gender		
Age group	Person	304
0-6	Male	131
	Female	173
Social Status	ST	18 M=5
	SC	F=13
	General/OBC	2260 M=1131
		F=1129
		550
Workers	Total Workers	857
	Male	733
	Female	124
	Main Workers	761
	Marginal Workers	96 M=45
		F=51
Occupation	Service	125
	Business	178
	Daily Wage	192
	Others	362
Literacy Rate	Total	86.29%
	Male	92.23%
	Female	80.20%
Education	Primary school	2
	Middle school	2
	Secondary school	1
	Anganwari kendra	8
Housing	Pucca	255
	Semi- Pucca	382
	Kutchra	58
Electrification	Yes/No	Yes

Public Transport Facility	Yes/No	Yes

Table: 2 Land Cover

LAND COVER	AREA IN HECTARE
Total Land	66.3
Tea Garden	27 bigha
Area under non-agricultural use	58
Culturable waste land	8.3

Source: District census handbook, 2011 and field survey

Table: 3 Occupation of the respondents, their father's and Grandfather's

Occupation	Respondent's Occupation (in percentage)	Father's Occupation (in percentage)	Grandfather's Occupation (in percentage)
Fishing	27	80	83
Lumbering	6	5	0
Boat Service	2	0	5
Daily Wage Labour	18	5	2
Vegetable Seller	9	1	0
Shopkeeper	19	6	3
Agriculture	5	0	6
Service	10	3	1
Others	4	0	0

Source: Primary Data

5. Conclusion

In the Biswanath town village, agriculture based livelihood options are minimum among the village inhabitants, because there is a shortage of agricultural land in the village. As the village is religious place and it is also a perfect tourist destination during the winters. So, there is a great scope for tourism based livelihood options in the village. Fishing is also an important livelihood sustenance activity in the village, as the village is located in the bank of the river Brahmaputra. With proper implication of employment generic schemes and training and with the development of Self Help Group may help to bring out tourism based enterprises and fishing based enterprises in the village.

Ethical Clearance: It is a survey article

Source of Fund: Self

Conflict of Interest: Nil

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